

ICT BASED ENGLISH PEDAGOGY IN INDIAN CONTEXT

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Preface

ICT (Information and Communication Technology) is a term used to describe the various technologies and tools that are used for the acquisition, processing, storage, and communication of information. ICT is an important aspect of modern life as it has revolutionized the way we live, work, and communicates with each other. With the advent of ICT, information can be accessed, processed, and communicated more quickly and efficiently than ever before. Some examples of ICT include computers, smart phones, the internet, social media, email, video conferencing, and online collaboration tools. These technologies have not only made communication faster and more convenient but have also opened up new avenues for learning, innovation, and economic growth. ICT has become an essential part of our daily lives, shaping the way we interact with each other and the world around us. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has revolutionized the education sector by providing new avenues for teaching and learning. The integration of ICT tools such as computers, tablets, and the internet has transformed traditional teaching methods, making education more engaging, interactive, and accessible to students. ICT has enabled teachers to create multimedia content, interactive simulations, and online assessments, enhancing the learning experience. Moreover, ICT tools have enabled distance learning, e-learning, and remote access to educational resources, making education more inclusive and affordable. The use of ICT in education has also provided opportunities for personalized learning, collaborative learning, and real-time feedback, thereby improving the quality of education.

Place of ICT in Indian Education system

In India, the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has gained significant momentum over the years. The government of India has launched several initiatives to promote ICT-based education in the country. Some of the key initiatives include the National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NME-ICT), the Digital India campaign, and the SWAYAM platform.

Through these initiatives, the government aims to promote digital literacy, provide access to digital resources and tools, and enhance the quality of education in the country. ICT tools such as e-learning platforms, digital textbooks, multimedia content, and online assessments have been introduced to make education more engaging and interactive. ICT-based education has provided access to quality education to students in remote and underserved areas through online classes and digital content. The government has also launched several online platforms such as SWAYAM, NPTEL, and e-PG Pathshala that provide free access to educational resources, courses, and lectures.

ICT-based education has also facilitated personalized and adaptive learning, making education more engaging and effective. The use of virtual reality and simulations has enhanced the learning experience for students. There are still challenges to be addressed in terms of access to technology and internet connectivity, particularly in rural and remote areas of the country. Nonetheless, the integration of ICT in education has the potential to transform the educational landscape in India and provide access to quality education to millions of students across the country.

Why India requires ICT based Pedagogy?

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an integral part of pedagogy in India. Here are some reasons why ICT is important in Indian education:

Access to Information: ICT provides access to a wealth of information that can be used to enhance teaching and learning. With the internet and other digital resources, students can access a vast array of educational materials that were previously unavailable to them.

Improves Learning Outcomes : The use of ICT in the classroom improves learning outcomes of students. For example, interactive multimedia presentations can make learning more engaging, and digital simulations can help students understand complex concepts.

Enhances Teaching : Teachers may use ICT based pedagogy to deliver lessons in more innovative and engaging ways so that learners find it interesting and entertaining. For example, they can use digital media to create interactive presentations, use social media to

engage with students outside of the classroom, and use online tools to provide real-time feedback.

Digital Literacy: ICT provides students with the digital literacy skills they need to succeed in the modern world. Students learn how to use technology for research, communication, and collaboration, which are essential skills in today's digital age.

Cost-effective: With the increasing use of ICT in education, it has become a cost-effective solution for delivering quality education to a large number of students. The use of ICT in pedagogy in India is essential for providing quality education to students and preparing them for the challenges of the modern world.

Traditional methods of teaching English

Traditional methods of teaching English language skills typically involve a teacher-centered approach, where the teacher is the primary source of knowledge and instruction, and the students are passive recipients of information. These methods include:

- **Grammar-Translation Method:** This method focuses on learning the rules of grammar and translating sentences from one language to another.
- **Direct Method:** This method emphasizes the development of oral communication skills through immersion in the target language.
- **Audio-Lingual Method:** This method emphasizes the development of listening and speaking skills through drills and repetition.
- **Communicative Language Teaching:** This method emphasizes the development of communicative competence through real-life situations and activities.
- **Task-Based Language Teaching:** This method focuses on the development of language skills through the completion of real-life tasks.
- **Total Physical Response:** This method emphasizes the development of language skills through the use of physical actions and movements.

These traditional methods have been used for many years and have been successful in teaching English language skills to students. However, they have been criticized for being too teacher-centered and not providing enough opportunities for students to practice and develop their language skills. Additionally, these methods may not be suitable for all learners and more innovative and inclusive approaches may be required to meet the diverse needs of students.

ICT-based pedagogy in context of India

ICT-based pedagogy has been increasingly adopted in India in recent years to enhance teaching and learning in schools and universities. The government of India has taken several

initiatives to promote the integration of ICT in education, such as the National Policy on Education (NPE) and the Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA). ICT-based pedagogy is a teaching and learning approach that utilizes information and communication technology tools and resources to enhance the learning experience. It involves the integration of technology into teaching methods and practices to facilitate personalized and adaptive learning. ICT-based pedagogy enables teachers to create multimedia content, simulations, and interactive assessments that engage and motivate students. It also provides opportunities for collaborative learning and real-time feedback, making the learning process more effective and efficient.

ICT-based pedagogy includes various tools such as educational software, learning management systems, virtual reality etc. These tools help to make learning more interactive and enjoyable, which in turn leads to better retention of knowledge. ICT-based pedagogy promotes self-directed and lifelong learning by providing access to digital resources and online courses. It also enables remote learning and distance education, making education more accessible to students who are unable to attend traditional classroom settings. ICT-based pedagogy is an innovative approach to teaching and learning that has the potential to transform the education system by making it more inclusive, engaging, and effective.

ICT-based English pedagogy is a teaching and learning approach that utilizes information and communication technology tools and resources to enhance the teaching and learning of English language skills. It involves the integration of technology into teaching methods and practices to facilitate personalized and adaptive learning.

ICT-based English pedagogy includes various tools such as **language learning software, digital resources, online dictionaries, and virtual learning environments**. These tools help to create an interactive and engaging learning environment, allowing students to learn English language skills at their own pace and level. ICT-based English pedagogy also facilitates collaboration and communication, enabling students to practice and develop their language skills through online discussions, video conferencing, and social media.

ICT-based English pedagogy helps to develop digital literacy skills, which are essential in today's world. It also provides access to authentic language materials and resources, which are difficult to obtain in traditional classroom settings. ICT-based English pedagogy is an innovative approach to teaching and learning English language skills that has the potential to transform the way English is taught and learned by making it more engaging, effective, and accessible.

Here are some examples of ICT-based pedagogy initiatives in India:

- **Digital Classrooms:** Many schools and colleges in India have implemented digital classrooms, which use multimedia content such as videos, animations, and simulations to supplement traditional classroom instruction.
- **Online Learning Platforms:** Online learning platforms, such as the National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL) and SWAYAM, provide students with access to online courses and resources to support their learning.
- **Educational Apps:** Educational apps, such as Diksha, provide students with access to digital textbooks, videos, and quizzes to support their learning.
- **Virtual Labs:** Virtual labs provide students with access to simulated laboratory experiments, which can be especially helpful in areas where physical labs may be limited.
- **Webinars and Online Workshops:** Webinars and online workshops provide teachers and students with the opportunity to interact with experts in their field and to learn about new teaching and learning strategies.

The adoption of ICT-based pedagogy in India has the potential to improve the quality of education and to make learning more accessible to students in rural and remote areas. However, it is important to ensure that all students have access to the necessary technology and infrastructure to participate fully in ICT-based learning initiatives.

NEP-2020 and ICT

According to NEP 2020, an autonomous body, the **National Educational Technology Forum (NETF)**, is going to be created to supply a platform for the free exchange of ideas on the utilization of technology to reinforce learning, assessment, planning, administration, and so on, both for college and better education. The aim of the NETF are going to be to facilitate deciding on the induction, deployment, and use of technology, by providing to the leadership of education institutions, State and Central governments, and other stakeholders, the newest knowledge and research also because the opportunity to consult and share best practices. The NETF will have the subsequent functions:

- provide independent evidence-based advice to Central and government agencies on technology-based interventions;
- build proper infrastructure in educational technology;
- envision strategic thrust areas during this domain; and
- Articulate new directions for research and innovation.

The thrust of technological interventions is going to be for the needs of improving teaching learning and evaluation processes, supporting teacher preparation and professional development, enhancing educational access, and streamlining educational planning, management, and administration including processes associated with admissions, attendance, assessments, etc. an upscale sort of educational software, for all the above purposes, are going to be developed and made available for college kids and teachers in the least levels. Teaching-learning e-content will still be developed by all States altogether regional languages, also as by the NCERT, CIET, CBSE, NIOS, and other bodies/institutions, and can be uploaded onto the DIKSHA platform. Particular attention will got to be paid to emerging disruptive technologies which will necessarily transform the education system. one among the permanent tasks of the NETF are going to be to categorize emergent technologies supported their potential and estimated timeframe for disruption, and to periodically present this analysis to MHRD. supported these inputs, MHRD will formally identify those technologies whose emergence demands responses from the education system.

Given the emergence of digital technologies and therefore the emerging importance of leveraging technology for teaching-learning in the least levels from school to education, this Policy recommends the subsequent key initiatives:

- (a) **Pilot studies for online education:** Appropriate agencies, like the NETF, CIET, NIOS, IGNOU, IITs, NITs, etc. will be identified to conduct a series of pilot studies, to evaluate the benefits of integrating education with online education.
- (b) **Digital infrastructure:** This will ensure that the technology-based solutions do not become outdated with the rapid advances in technology.
- (c) **Online teaching platform and tools:** Appropriate existing e-learning platforms like SWAYAM, DIKSHA, are going to be extended to supply teachers with a structured, user-friendly, rich set of assistive tools for monitoring progress of learners.
- (d) **Content creation, digital repository, and dissemination:** A digital repository of content including creation of coursework, Learning Games & Simulations, Augmented Reality and computer game are going to be developed. A reliable backup mechanism for disseminating e-content to students is going to be provided.
- (e) **Addressing the digital divide:** A special focus on content in all Indian languages will be emphasized and required; digital content will need to reach the teachers and students in their medium of instruction as far as possible.

(f) **Virtual Labs:** Existing e-learning platforms like DIKSHA, SWAYAM and SWAYAMPBHA also will be leveraged for creating virtual labs in order that all students have equal access to quality practical and hands-on experiment-based learning experiences.

(g) **Training and incentives for teachers:** Teachers will undergo rigorous training in learner-centric pedagogy and on the way to become high-quality online content creators themselves using online teaching platforms and tools.

(h) **Online assessment and examinations:** Appropriate bodies, like the proposed National Assessment Centre or PARAKH, School Boards, NTA, and other identified bodies will design and implement assessment frameworks. They will also design required competencies, portfolio, rubrics, standardized assessments, and assessment analytics.

(i) **Blended models of learning:** For implementing digital learning in education, the importance of face-to-face in-person learning is fully recognized. Accordingly, different effective models of blended learning are going to be identified for appropriate replication for various subjects

Tools for Enhanced and Modernised Learning of English Language through ICT

I. Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL)

Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is the use of technology to enhance language learning. It can include the use of software, web-based resources, and multimedia materials. Here are some examples of CALL tools that can be used for language learning:

Language Learning Software: There are many language learning software programs available, such as Rosetta Stone, Duolingo, and Babbel. These programs offer interactive lessons that can improve listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills.

Online Dictionaries and Grammar Guides: Online dictionaries and grammar guides are a useful resource for language learners. They can provide instant translations and explanations of grammar rules, helping learners to better understand the language.

Multimedia Language Learning Resources: Multimedia resources, such as videos, podcasts, and interactive activities, can be a fun and engaging way to learn a language. YouTube, TED Talks, and News in Slow are examples of multimedia resources that can be used for language learning.

Language Learning Games: Games, such as Hangman, Scrabble, and Memory, can be used to improve vocabulary and spelling skills. Online games, such as Kahoot and Quizlet, can be a fun way to engage learners and reinforce language learning.

Virtual Language Exchange Platforms: Virtual language exchange platforms, such as iTalki and HelloTalk, connect language learners with native speakers for conversation

practice. These platforms provide an opportunity for learners to practice speaking and listening skills in a real-world context.

II. **Mobile Apps:** There are many tools available for teaching English through ICT (Information and Communication Technology). Here are some popular ones:

Duolingo: Duolingo is a free language learning platform that offers courses in many languages, including English. It is a gamified app that offers engaging lessons that include speaking, listening, and writing exercises.

Rosetta Stone: Rosetta Stone is a language learning platform that uses interactive software and live online classes to teach languages. It offers courses in many languages, including English, and it is suitable for beginners as well as advanced learners.

Edmodo: Edmodo is a social learning platform that allows teachers to create an online learning community for their students. It offers features such as discussion forums, quizzes, and assignments, which can be used to teach English.

Kahoot: Kahoot is a game-based learning platform that can be used to teach English through quizzes, surveys, and discussions. It is a fun way to engage students and improve their English skills.

Quizlet: Quizlet is a learning platform that offers flashcards, quizzes, and study games. It can be used to teach English vocabulary and grammar, and it is suitable for learners of all levels.

Google Classroom: Google Classroom is a free learning management system that can be used to create and manage online classes. It offers features such as assignments, quizzes, and discussion forums, which can be used to teach English.

Grammarly: Grammarly is an online writing tool that can be used to improve English grammar and writing skills. It offers suggestions for grammar, spelling, and punctuation, which can be very useful for English learners.

These are just a few examples of the many tools available for teaching English through ICT. Each tool offers its own unique features and benefits, so it is important to choose the one that best fits your teaching style and the needs of your students.

III. Language labs

Language labs are specialized computer-based facilities that are designed to support language learning and teaching. They provide language learners with access to a variety of resources, such as audio and video materials, and allow learners to practice their language skills in a controlled environment. In the context of English learning, language labs can be particularly effective in improving students' listening and speaking skills.

Here are some of the ways in which language labs can be used to support English learning:

Listening Comprehension: Language labs provide students access to a range of listening materials, such as dialogues, speeches, and recordings of native speakers. Students can listen to these materials at their own pace, and can practice their listening comprehension skills through a range of activities, such as dictation exercises and comprehension quizzes.

Pronunciation Practice: Language labs often include speech recognition software, which can help students to improve their pronunciation skills. Students can practice speaking English into a microphone, and the software can provide instant feedback on their pronunciation.

Speaking Practice : Language labs provide students a controlled environment in which they practice their speaking skills. They can practice speaking English in pairs or small groups, and can receive feedback from their teacher or peers.

Language Games and Exercises: Language labs often include interactive language games and exercises, which can be used to reinforce vocabulary and grammar concepts.

Language labs can be an effective tool for supporting English learning, particularly in developing listening and speaking skills. However, it is important to note that language labs should be used in conjunction with other teaching methods, such as classroom instruction and individualized tutoring, to provide a comprehensive language learning experience.

IV. Simulations

Simulation-based English teaching is an approach that involves using simulations to create real-world scenarios that allow students to practice and develop their language skills in a contextualized and authentic way. This approach to teaching English has become increasingly popular in recent years because it allows students to experience real-life situations in a safe and controlled environment, which can be particularly helpful for language learners. The computer can act as a stimulus which generates analysis, critical thinking, discussion and writing. Program which include simulations are especially effective as stimuli. Examples of language learning tasks which ‘simulate’ real world tasks are : 1) Web Quest; 2) Action Mazes; 3) Adventure games; 4) Sunpower; 5) Expodisc; 6) “Real-life” simulations; 7) video conference.

Conclusion

ICT appears to give both advantages and disadvantages. ICT in language learning reduces the intimacy of students – teacher relationship that it may negatively contributes to students affective feelings in the process of learning. However, ICT appears as a ‘bridge’ to break the distance and ‘survive’ the learning. In case of distance, teachers can use ICT through video conference to enable them teach or monitor the students learning process. Therefore, the

development of ICT is seen as a better way of teaching and learning a certain language compared to the existing methods. Through the internet, teacher or learners can obtain as many as possible sources related to the learned – language; such as text, songs, stories, etc. Those sources can contribute as models of the learned – language use in the real context and in a proper manner. In addition, computer can also be used as a more interactive aid to support the learning of language compared to that of tape recorder, or chalk and blackboard. However, you can see that many of the technology solutions available in the world of education can lead to confusion among the teachers on how to choose the right ICT technology solutions. Let's take a look at the advantages and disadvantages of ICT tools for education and finding a suitable ICT education solution for the needs of the school. ICT is a form of advanced science technology must be optimized function, especially in the implementation of learning. ICT provides opportunities for students in the era of global competition needs to obtain adequate supplies. through innovative ICT-based learning can provide vast opportunities for students to hone and promote competence on an international scale. Mastering current tick is necessity for every human being inedible age. as well as in education, innovative learning, especially learning can be done by using the Internet to generate device-based learning ICT.

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